

Synthesis and antibacterial activity of some chalcones

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Abstract : The chalcones derived from quinoline aldehyde were (2*E*)-3-(2-chlorobenzo[*h*]quinolin-3-yl)-1-(4-methoxyphenyl)prop-2-en-1-one (RM-1), (2*E*)-3-(2-chlorobenzo[*h*]quinolin-3-yl)-1-(4-methylphenyl)prop-2-en-1-one (RM-2), (2*E*)-3-(2-chlorobenzo[*h*]quinolin-3-yl)-1-(4-chlorophenyl)prop-2-en-1-one (RM-3), (2*E*)-1-(4-bromophenyl)-3-(2-chlorobenzo[*h*]quinolin-3-yl)prop-2-en-1-one (RM-4), (2*E*)-3-(2-chlorobenzo[*h*]quinolin-3-yl)-1-(4-nitrophenyl)prop-2-en-1-one (RM-5), (2*E*)-1-(4-aminophenyl)-3-(2-chlorobenzo[*h*]quinolin-3-yl)prop-2-en-1-one (RM-6), (2*E*)-3-(2-chlorobenzo[*h*]quinolin-3-yl)-1-(3-nitrophenyl)prop-2-en-1-one (RM-7), (2*E*)-3-(2-chlorobenzo[*h*]quinolin-3-yl)-1-(2-hydroxyphenyl)prop-2-en-1-one (RM-8), (2*E*)-3-(2-chlorobenzo[*h*]quinolin-3-yl)-1-(4-hydroxyphenyl)prop-2-en-1-one (RM-9), (2*E*)-3-(2-chlorobenzo[*h*]quinolin-3-yl)-1-phenylprop-2-en-1-one (RM-10).

Chalcones were evaluated for their potential as antibacterial agents against three Gram-positive bacteria *Bacillus cereus*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Micrococcus flavus* and three Gram-negative bacteria *Proteus mirabilis*, *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. The antibacterial assay was evaluated by agar disc diffusion method in DMF solvent.

Keywords : Quinoline aldehyde, chalcones, antibacterial activity, DMF.

Introduction

The chemistry of chalcones has generated intensive scientific studies throughout the world, due to their biological and industrial applications. Various methods are available in the literature for the synthesis of chalcones¹⁻³. The most convenient method is one that involves the Claisen condensation of equimolar quantities of an aryl methyl ketone with aryl aldehyde in presence of alcoholic alkali⁴. The chalcones have been found to be useful for the synthesis of variety of heterocyclic compounds such as cyanopyridone⁵, pyridopyrimidines⁶, amino pyrimidines⁷, 3-cyanopyridines⁸, isoxazoles⁹, thiazepines¹⁰, pyrazolines¹¹, oxirane¹², 1,4-oxazepines¹³, 2-isothiazolidines¹⁴, barbitone¹⁵, oxopyrimidines¹⁶, 1-carboxamide pyrazolines¹⁷, 2-1*H*-pyrimidines¹⁸, imine derivatives¹⁹. Literature survey shows that chalcones are associated with different biological activities²⁰⁻²². Boeck *et al.*²³ have reported analogs containing nitro, fluorine or bromine group respectively displayed increased selectivity against

the parasites as compared with natural chalcones.

The present paper describes the synthesis of some new chalcones from the quinoline aldehyde, characterization through IR, NMR and mass spectral studies and reports of their antibacterial activity. The antibacterial activity was tested against three Gram-positive bacteria *B. cereus*, *S. aureus* and *M. flavus* and three Gram-negative bacteria *P. mirabilis*, *E. coli* and *K. pneumoniae*. The determination of antibacterial activity was done using the agar disc diffusion method. The antibacterial activity was evaluated in *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF).

Experimental

The following chalcones were synthesized :

RM-1 : (2*E*)-3-(2-chlorobenzo[*h*]quinolin-3-yl)-1-(4-methoxyphenyl)prop-2-en-1-one

RM-2 : (2*E*)-3-(2-chlorobenzo[*h*]quinolin-3-yl)-1-(4-methylphenyl)prop-2-en-1-one

RM-3 : (2*E*)-3-(2-chlorobenzo[*h*]quinolin-3-yl)-1-(4-

chlorophenyl)prop-2-en-1-one

RM-4 : (2*E*)-1-(4-bromophenyl)-3-(2-chlorobenzo[*h*]quinolin-3-yl)prop-2-en-1-one

RM-5 : (2*E*)-3-(2-chlorobenzo[*h*]quinolin-3-yl)-1-(4-nitrophenyl)prop-2-en-1-one

RM-6 : (2*E*)-1-(4-aminophenyl)-3-(2-chlorobenzo[*h*]quinolin-3-yl)prop-2-en-1-one

RM-7 : (2*E*)-3-(2-chlorobenzo[*h*]quinolin-3-yl)-1-(3-nitrophenyl)prop-2-en-1-one

RM-8 : (2*E*)-3-(2-chlorobenzo[*h*]quinolin-3-yl)-1-(2-hydroxyphenyl)prop-2-en-1-one

RM-9 : (2*E*)-3-(2-chlorobenzo[*h*]quinolin-3-yl)-1-(4-hydroxyphenyl)prop-2-en-1-one

RM-10 : (2*E*)-3-(2-chlorobenzo[*h*]quinolin-3-yl)-1-phenylprop-2-en-1-one

Synthesis of chalcones : To a well stirred solution of 2-chlorobenzo[*h*]quinoline-3-carbaldehyde (2.41 g, 0.01 *M*) and *p*-methoxyacetophenone (1.50 g, 0.01 *M*) in ethanol (25 ml), 40% NaOH was added till the solution was basic. The reaction mixture was stirred for 48 h. The contents were poured into ice, acidified, filtered and crystallized from ethanol.

The reaction scheme of all the synthesized compounds is given below.

Test microorganisms :

The bacterial strains studied are identified strains and were obtained from National Chemical Laboratory (NCL), Pune, India. The synthesized chalcones were tested for its antibacterial activity against three Gram-positive bacteria *Bacillus cereus* ATCC11778, *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC25923 and *Micrococcus flavus* ATCC10240 and three Gram-negative bacteria *Proteus mirabilis* NCIM2241, *Escherichia coli* ATCC25922 and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* NCIM2719.

Preparation of solutions of test compounds :

The synthesized test compounds were dissolved in DMF at a concentration of 10 mg/ml.

Preparation of the plates and microbiological assays :

The antibacterial assay was evaluated by the method of agar disc diffusion method^{24,25}. The media used for the antibacterial assay were Mueller Hinton Agar No. 2. The test strain (200 μ L) was inoculated into the media (inoculum size 10^8 cells/ml) when the temperature reached 40–42 °C and poured into Petri dishes. 20 μ L of the test compound was impregnated in to sterile discs (7 mm, Hi-Media) and allowed to dry and was introduced on the upper layer of the seeded agar plate. The plates were incubated overnight at 37 °C. The experiment was performed under strict aseptic conditions. Microbial growth was determined by measuring the diameter of zone of inhibition. For each bacterial strain, controls were maintained where pure solvent was used instead of the extract. The result was obtained by measuring the zone diameter. The experiment was done three times and the mean values are presented.

Results and discussion

In total 10 compounds were synthesized. Analysis of IR, NMR and mass spectral data (molecular ion peak) of all the synthesized compounds confirmed their molecular structure. Their data are given below.

RM-1 : IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 2931 (C–H str. asym.), 2837 (C–H str. sym.), 1509 (C=C str.), 833 (C–H o.o.p.), 1303 (C–N str.), 1661 (C=O str.), 1259 (C–O–C str. asym.), 1027 (C–O–C str. sym.), 751 (C–Cl str.); ¹H NMR (δ , ppm) : 7.25–8.33 (11H, m, Ar-H), 2.32 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃), 8.90 (1H, d, CH=C), 8.56 (1H, d, C=CH). Mass (*m/z*, rel. int. %) 374 (42), 338 (27), 150 (38), 135 (43), 107 (54), 77 (69), 44 (98).

RM-2 : IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 2948 (C–H str. asym.), 2857 (C–H str. sym.), 1529 (C=C str.), 1307 (C–N str.), 1675 (C=O str.), 1251 (C–O–C str. asym.), 1021 (C–O–C str. sym.), 758 (C–Cl str.); ¹H NMR (δ , ppm) : 7.66 (11H, m, Ar-H), 1.45 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃), 9.21 (1H, d, CH=C), 9.10 (1H, d, C=CH). Mass (*m/z*, rel. int. %) : 358 (35), 321 (28), 214 (48), 109 (42), 77 (745), 43 (99).

RM-3 : IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 2912 (C–H str. asym.), 2817 (C–H str. sym.), 1559 (C=C str.), 1334 (C–N str.), 1651 (C=O str.), 1257 (C–O–C str. asym.), 1021 (C–O–C str. sym.), 742 (C–Cl str.); ¹H NMR (δ , ppm) : 7.32–7.91 (11H, m, Ar-H), 9.06 (1H, d, CH=C), 9.18 (1H, d, C=CH). Mass (*m/z*, rel. int. %) : 378 (29), 329 (21), 205 (19), 77 (57), 43 (96).

RM-4 : IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 2942 (C-H str. asym.), 2819 (C-H str. sym.), 1545 (C=C str.), 1662 (C=O str.), 1021 (C-O-C str. sym.), 719 (C-Cl str.); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (δ , ppm) : 7.62–8.33 (11H, m, Ar-H), 9.16 (1H, d, CH=C), 8.86 (1H, d, C=CH). Mass (m/z , rel. int. %) : 422 (44), 309 (20), 179 (17), 143 (29), 77 (62), 43 (89).

RM-5 : IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 2908 (C-H str. asym.), 2859 (C-H str. sym.), 1524 (C=C str.), 1666 (C=O str.), 710 (C-Cl str.); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (δ , ppm) : 7.34–7.86 (11H, m, Ar-H), 8.96 (1H, d, CH=C), 8.59 (1H, d, C=CH). Mass (m/z , rel. int. %) : 388 (33), 251 (31), 127 (28), 77 (78), 43 (99).

RM-6 : IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 2957 (C-H str. asym.), 2846 (C-H str. sym.), 1547 (C=C str.), 1657 (C=O str.), 713 (C-Cl str.); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (δ , ppm) : 7.16–7.76 (11H, m, Ar-H), 4.37 (1H, d, $-\text{NH}_2$), 9.90 (1H, d, CH=C), 9.59 (1H, d, C=CH). Mass (m/z , rel. int. %) : 358 (37), 302 (21), 267 (14), 244 (31), 149 (47), 77 (56), 43 (94).

8.79 (1H, d, C=CH). Mass (m/z , rel. int. %) : 359 (21), 322 (17), 247 (415), 144 (51), 77 (63), 43 (99).

RM-9 : IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 2926 (C-H str. asym.), 2862 (C-H str. sym.), 1528 (C=C str.), 1670 (C=O str.), 760 (C-Cl str.); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (δ , ppm) : 7.31–7.79 (11H, m, Ar-H), 5.24 (1H, s, -OH), 9.10 (1H, d, CH=C), 8.84 (1H, d, C=CH). Mass (m/z , rel. int. %) : 359 (39), 341 (21), 269 (18), 142 (45), 77 (58), 43 (97).

RM-10 : IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 2966 (C-H str. asym.), 2860 (C-H str. sym.), 1535 (C=C str.), 1675 (C=O str.), 766 (C-Cl str.); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (δ , ppm) : 7.12–7.69 (12H, m, Ar-H), 8.86 (1H, d, CH=C), 8.68 (1H, d, C=CH). Mass (m/z , rel. int. %) : 343 (25), 341 (14), 282 (45), 176 (33), 107 (56), 77 (62), 43 (99).

The molecular formula, molecular weights, melting points, % yields and R_f values along with the solvent system of the chalcones are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Physical constants of chalcones

Sl. no.	Code	R'	M.F.	M.wt. (g/mol)	R_f^a value	M.p. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Yield (%)
1.	RM-1	4-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ ClNO ₂	373.83	0.42	212	55
2.	RM-2	4-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ ClNO	357.83	0.59	189	62
3.	RM-3	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ Cl ₂ NO	378.25	0.51	202	57
4.	RM-4	4-Br-C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ ClBrNO	422.70	0.55	222	64
5.	RM-5	4-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ ClN ₂ O ₃	388.80	0.57	187	59
6.	RM-6	4-NH ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ ClN ₂ O	358.82	0.39	168	70
7.	RM-7	3-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ ClN ₂ O ₃	388.80	0.42	201	60
8.	RM-8	2-OH-C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ ClNO ₂	359.80	0.66	195	57
9.	RM-9	4-OH-C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ ClNO ₂	359.80	0.64	228	58
10.	RM-10	C ₆ H ₅ -	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ ClNO	343.80	0.41	181	64

^aAcetone : benzene : 2 : 8.

RM-7 : IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 2944 (C-H str. asym.), 2834 (C-H str. sym.), 1572 (C=C str.), 1675 (C=O str.), 743 (C-Cl str.); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (δ , ppm) : 7.56–8.12 (11H, m, Ar-H), 9.51 (1H, d, CH=C), 9.25 (1H, d, C=CH). Mass (m/z , rel. int. %) : 388 (26), 302 (39), 107 (45), 77 (61), 43 (98).

RM-8 : IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 2957 (C-H str. asym.), 2842 (C-H str. sym.), 1528 (C=C str.), 1654 (C=O str.), 763 (C-Cl str.); $^1\text{H NMR}$ (δ , ppm) : 7.22–7.89 (11H, m, Ar-H), 5.37 (1H, s, -OH), 9.21 (1H, d, CH=C),

All the chalcones are tested against three Gram-positive and three Gram-negative bacteria. The activities of various compounds are shown as below.

Fig. 1 shows the zone of inhibition against Gram-positive bacteria. It is observed that against *B. cereus*, **RM-10** showed maximum inhibition followed by **RM-3** and **RM-8**. Minimum inhibition was observed by **RM-4** and **RM-7**.

All the compounds have the same central moiety quino-line aldehydes, but different substitution groups. **RM-10**

Fig. 1. Antibacterial activity against Gram-positive bacteria.

contains phenyl ring without any substitution whereas RM-3 and RM-8 contains *p*-chloro- and *o*-hydroxy-acetophenone respectively. This suggests that activity against *B. cereus*, substituted phenyl ring decreases the inhibition and it is minimum when bromo and nitro groups are attached at *para* and *meta* positions in the phenyl ring respectively. In case of *S. aureus*, RM-1 showed maximum inhibition whereas RM-4 showed minimum inhibition. Thus, in this case, *p*-methoxy acetophenone increases the inhibition whereas *p*-bromo acetophenone again causes a decrease in inhibition.

Against *M. flavus*, RM-3 containing *p*-chloro acetophenone showed maximum inhibition whereas the presence of *p*-hydroxy acetophenone (as in RM-9) causes a decrease in inhibition against these bacteria.

Fig. 2 shows the zone of inhibition against Gram-negative bacteria. It is evident from this figure that compounds RM-1 and RM-10 exhibited maximum activity

against *P. mirabilis*. Thus, *p*-methoxy acetophenone and acetophenone without any substituents are more effective. RM-5, RM-6 and RM-7 showed no activity suggesting *p*-nitro, *p*-amino and *m*-nitro acetophenone had no effect at all. RM-4, RM-8 and RM-9 showed minimum activity. These compounds contain *p*-bromo, *o*-hydroxy and *p*-hydroxy acetophenone respectively. Thus, nitro and amino groups do not affect *P. mirabilis* at all. However, hydroxy acetophenone has little effect, whereas the presence of methyl group and chloro group at *p*-position of acetophenone causes intermediate inhibition.

E. coli is not affected by RM-1, RM-2 and RM-5 at all. However, other compounds showed less inhibition.

Against *K. pneumoniae*, RM-9 showed maximum inhibition followed by RM-10. RM-1 showed minimum inhibition which contains *p*-methoxy acetophenone. RM-9 contains *p*-hydroxy acetophenone whereas RM-10 contains only acetophenone. The hydroxyl group is also

Note

Fig. 2. Antibacterial activity against Gram-negative bacteria.

present in RM-8, but at *ortho* position. This suggests that not only the substitution group but also their position, affect the inhibition.

Conclusion :

It can be concluded that presence or absence of antibacterial activity depends not only on the central moiety but also on the attached groups and their position. These findings support our earlier conclusion that the antibacterial activity is dependent on the molecular structure of the compound, the solvent used and the bacterial strain under consideration²⁶. In the present study, *E. coli* was the most resistant bacteria while *B. cereus* was most susceptible bacteria.

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